

Conference Abstract

Applicability of the Ella system for automatic Elisa to detect biomarkers in endometriosis

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Received: 11 Dec 2025 | Published: 07 Jan 2026

Citation: Mihaylova E, Vazharova R, Lechova-Dimitrova R, Dimova I, Nikolova D (2026) Applicability of the Ella system for automatic Elisa to detect biomarkers in endometriosis. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 9: e182179. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.9.e182179>

Abstract

Aim. Endometriosis is a chronic gynecological disorder characterized by ectopic endometrial tissue, inflammation, and angiogenesis. Non-invasive biomarkers in serum and urine could improve diagnosis and disease monitoring. This study evaluates the applicability of the Ella automated ELISA system for quantifying key endometriosis-associated biomarkers.

Methods. The Ella platform (ProteinSimple/Bio-Techne) allows automated, multiplexed quantification of cytokines, chemokines, and growth factors from minimal sample volumes. Plasma and urine were considered as matrices for biomarker detection. System performance, including sensitivity, reproducibility, and multiplexing capability, was assessed based on previously reported biomarker levels in women with and without endometriosis.

Results. Previous studies reported elevated levels of IGFBP-1 (UniProt Consortium 2025b, National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025c), CD5L Hong 2025 ,ANXA1 (Fang 2024), MCP-1 (National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025b), VEGF-A (Didžiokaitė 2025), TNF- α (National Center for Biotechnology Information 2025a), and

IL-6 in serum (UniProt Consortium 2025a), reflecting systemic inflammation and angiogenic activity. Urine samples showed increased IL-6 (UniProt Consortium 2025a), IL-8 (UniProt Consortium. 2025a), VEGF (Didžiokaitė 2025), IL-6-ST (National Center for Biotechnology Information. 2025), Alpha-Enolase (UniProt Consortium. 2025b), VDBP (Fernando 2020), and CA125 (Felder 2014), indicating both local and systemic disease-related changes. For better visual representation, the proteins described above and their functions are listed in Table 1. These findings support the feasibility of using automated ELISA platforms like Ella to detect disease-relevant biomarkers in both biofluids.

Conclusions. The Ella automated ELISA system provides a reliable and efficient approach for measuring serum and urinary biomarkers associated with endometriosis. Its multiplexing capacity and low sample requirements enable non-invasive biomarker studies, supporting early diagnosis, monitoring of disease progression, and evaluation of therapeutic interventions.

Table 1. Applicability of the Ella system for automatic Elisa to detect biomarkers in endometriosis.			
Gene	Full name	Protein	Function
IGFBP1	Insulin like growth factor binding protein 1	IGFBP-1	Regulates the bioavailability and activity of insulin-like growth factors; important in cell migration and metabolism
CD5L	CD5 molecule like	CD5L	Key regulator of lipid synthesis; regulates mechanisms in inflammatory responses
ANXA1	Annexin A1	ANXA1	Ubiquitous protein; Inhibits phospholipase A2 and has anti-inflammatory activity
CCL-2	C-C motif chemokine ligand 2	MCP-1	Regulates leukocyte recruitment; Chemotactic activity for monocytes and basophils
TNF	Tumor necrosis factor	TNF- α	Involved in the regulation of a wide spectrum of biological processes including cell proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, lipid metabolism, and coagulation
VEGF-A	Vascular endothelial growth factor A	VEGF-A	Key mediator of angiogenesis and inflammation; Implicated in reproductive and immune processes
IL-6	Interleukin 6	IL-6	Potent inducer of the acute phase response; Induces the production of VEGF
CXCL8	C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 8	IL-8	Mediates inflammatory response by attracting neutrophils, basophils, and T-cells to clear pathogens and protect the host from infection
IL6ST	Interleukin 6 cytokine family signal transducer	IL-6ST	Part of the cytokine-receptor complex; Suggested role in regulating myocyte apoptosis

Gene	Full name	Protein	Function
ENO1	Enolase 1	Alpha-enolase	Glycolytic enzyme; Involved in various processes such as growth control, hypoxia tolerance and allergic responses
GC	GC vitamin D binding protein	Vitamin D-binding protein	Immunoregulation, glucose metabolism, and regulation of blood pressure; involved in maintaining an environment of tolerance to paternal and fetal tissue and the augmentation of pro-inflammatory states
MUC16	Mucin 16, cell surface associated	CA 125	Immune attack resistance; Plays role in metastasis; Contributes to ovarian tumor growth

Keywords

automated Elisa (Ella), endometriosis, biomarkers

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Presented at

International Conference on Natural Sciences and Biotechnology – Kliment's Days 2025

Acknowledgements

This study is a part of the project D-156/4.6.25 financed by the Council of Medical Science, Medical University - Sofia, Bulgaria.

Funding program

Project D-156/4.6.25

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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